

Travertine increases the concentration of trace elements in groundwater in Chahar Takab, Fariman County, northeast Iran

Maryam Rezanezhad^{1,2}, Mohamad Hosein Mahmudy-Gharaie², Nicola Fohrer¹, Daniel Rosado^{1,3}

¹Department of Hydrology and Water Resources Management, Institute for Natural Resource Conservation, Kiel University, 24118 Kiel, Germany

²Department of Geology, Faculty of Science, Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Mashhad, Iran

³Department of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, Universidad de Sevilla, 41092 Sevilla, Spain

HIGHLIGHTS:

- Travertine reduces groundwater quality
- Ca-HCO₃ dominates surface and groundwater
- Ca-Mg-Cl dominantes in travertine springs
- High concentrations of As, B, Fe, Mn, and Pb
- Toxicity risks associated with As, Cd, and Pb

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR:

* Department of Hydrology and Water Resources Management, Institute for Natural Resource Conservation, Kiel University, Olshausenstr. 75, D-24118 Kiel, Germany. Tel.: 0049 431 880 4889; E-mail address: drosado@hydrology.uni-kiel.de (Daniel Rosado).

Acknowledgments

The research was conducted jointly at Ferdowsi University of Mashhad (FUM), Iran, and Christian Albrechts University of Kiel (CAU), Germany. We are grateful to FUM and CAU for facilitating this research endeavor. Additionally, authors acknowledge financial support from the German Academic Exchange Service (DAAD).

Abstract	31
Groundwater has emerged as a crucial water source, supplying half of the world's domestic water needs, particularly in rural areas without supply systems. This study assesses the impact of travertine formations, on water quality in Chahar Takab village, Iran, focusing on suitability for human consumption and ecosystem sustainability where groundwater is the primary source.	32 33 34 35 36
Thirty-four samples from various sources, including travertine springs, surface water, and groundwater, underwent ICP-OES analysis. Travertine springs exhibited higher electrical conductivity (EC), lower pH, and elevated concentrations of major cations (Na, Ca, Mg) and anions (Cl, HCO ₃). In them, all samples exceeded European Union limits for Cl and Na in drinking water. Hydrochemical facies were influenced by water-rock interactions, leading to Ca-HCO ₃ dominance in surface and groundwater samples and Ca-Mg-Cl dominance in travertine springs.	37 38 39 40 41 42 43 44
Heavy metal analysis revealed high concentrations of As, B, Fe, Mn, and Pb in travertine spring and surface water samples, with As exceeding World Health Organization limits by up to 28.5 times. Additionally, the Metal Index indicated values exceeding drinking water guidelines set by the World Health Organization in 58% of the samples. Travertine springs had the highest toxicity risks, especially for As, Cd, and Pb. Results suggest a tectonic origin for heavy metal contamination (As-containing travertine springs), emphasizing the need for mitigation measures and regular monitoring. Action is necessary to address water quality issues in the region.	45 46 47 48 49 50 51 52 53
Keywords	54
Groundwater Quality, Arsenic, Heavy Metal Pollution, Drinking Water, Travertine Springs, Water Scarcity	55 56 57

1 Introduction

58

Two billion people worldwide lack access to safe drinking water (United Nations, 2022). Furthermore, half of the global population experiences severe water scarcity for at least part of the year (IPCC, 2022). This situation is projected to intensify in the future due to climate change and population growth (World Meteorological Organization, 2022). Consequently, groundwater has become a vital water source, supplying half of the world's domestic water needs (UNESCO World Water Assessment Programme, 2022). In rural areas without supply systems, it often serves as the only viable option for providing basic water access (UNESCO World Water Assessment Programme, 2022). Remarkably, the Asia-Pacific region leads global groundwater extraction, with seven of the top ten groundwater-extracting nations (Bangladesh, China, India, Indonesia, Iran, Pakistan and Turkey) accounting for approximately 60% of the world's total groundwater withdrawal (UNESCO World Water Assessment Programme, 2022).

59
60
61
62
63
64
65
66
67
68
69
70
71

Although groundwater resources are often abundant, their quality can be affected by industries, mining, urban effluents and other anthropogenic activities, as well as natural factors such as specific lithologies or the presence of travertine springs (Kumar et al., 2019; Vardhan et al., 2019). The chemical interactions between groundwater and minerals, known as hydrogeochemical processes, that involve mineral dissolution and precipitation, ion exchange, oxidation-reduction reactions, and adsorption-desorption mechanisms, together with the geological characteristics of an area, such as rock type, mineral composition, and structural features, largely influence the physicochemical characteristics of groundwater (Aju et al., 2022; Islam, 2023).

72
73
74
75
76
77
78
79
80
81

The so-called heavy metal (i.e. trace elements) are frequent pollutants of groundwater and their presence has become a global issue with potential adverse impacts on human health (Amaral et al., 2018; He and Wu, 2019a, 2019b; Masoudinejad et al., 2018). Groundwater is particularly affected by non-anthropogenic elements such as As, F, Cr, B, and others, which originate from geological formations, water-rock ion exchange, and degassing of magma intrusion (Delkhahi et al., 2020).

82
83
84
85
86
87
88

Among the mentioned heavy metals, especially inorganic As pollution in groundwater resources became a global challenge (Roh et al., 2017). Inorganic As constitutes the main form of As found in groundwater, surface water, and soil (Pazhoor et al., 2021). It can be present in water as Arsenite, As (III), the most toxic form of As, and as Arsenate, As (V), less toxic (Biswas et al., 2019; Chakraborti et al., 2016). The primary source of inorganic As in groundwater is

89
90
91
92
93
94

geological weathering, but also anthropogenic sources can be involved (Biswas and Sarkar, 2019). As has been categorized as a Group A carcinogen, denoting it as a 'known' human carcinogen, by both the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA, 2004) and the International Agency for Research on Cancer (American Cancer Society, 2020). This classification is based on the chronic toxicity effects of As in drinking water. To mitigate this risk, the World Health Organization (WHO) lowered the permissible limit for As in drinking water to 10 µg/l (Foster et al., 2019). Usually, As concentrations in uncontaminated surface water ranges from 1 to 10 µg/l. However, in mining and mineralization areas, these levels can significantly escalate (Kumar et al., 2019). Travertine rock is a unique type of limestone formed by the deposition of CaCO₃ from hydrothermal vents along fractures and faults in the Earth's crust (Grootjans et al., 2015; Henchiri et al., 2017; Kano et al., 2019; Pola et al., 2014; Shiraishi et al., 2020). Travertine is a sedimentary freshwater carbonate rock that forms from hydrothermal water springs rich in Ca²⁺ and with high partial pressure of CO₂ (Kano et al., 2019). When this water emerges at the surface, rapid CO₂ degassing occurs, increasing pH and triggering the precipitation of CaCO₃ according to the reaction: $\text{Ca}^{2+} + 2\text{HCO}_3^- \leftrightarrow \text{CaCO}_3 + \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Kano et al., 2019). Typically, travertine formation involves CO₂ and fluids of deep origin (Janssens et al., 2020). In contrast, tufa, another freshwater carbonate, forms in cool, ambient temperature freshwater environments through biologically induced processes and often contains remnants of micro- and macrophytes, invertebrates, and bacteria (Kele and Bódai, 2022). Additionally, tufa forms from shallow CO₂ sources, such as soil biodegradation or plants (Janssens et al., 2020).

Travertine springs waters are frequently rich in various elements, including potentially high levels of trace elements, due to the travertine rock-water interaction in deep aquifers (Durowoju et al., 2015). This process can directly reduce the quality of surface and groundwater or cause alterations through infiltration, discharge–recharge pattern of groundwater, inter-aquifer exchange, etc. Consequently, it can hinder the suitability of these waters for drinking and agricultural purposes (Kampouroglou and Economou-Eliopoulos, 2016; Rezaei et al., 2018).

The effects of travertine spring waters on trace elements, especially As, have attracted attention of researchers worldwide (Kano et al., 2019; Rezaei et al., 2018). Geothermal areas in Japan and locations with thermal activity in New Zealand have reported exceptionally high As concentrations in water, reaching 6400 µg/l and 8500 µg/l, respectively (Shakeri et al., 2020). Therefore, studies investigating As contamination have been conducted worldwide, including the

United States, China, Argentina, Chile, Bolivia, Peru, Mexico, Bangladesh,	133
Japan, India, Nepal, among others (Ayotte et al., 2015; Bhowmick et al., 2018;	134
He et al., 2020; Hossain et al., 2016; Huq et al., 2020; Mueller, 2017; Ortega-	135
Guerrero, 2017; Tapia et al., 2019) and has recently been reported in Iran	136
(Mohammadzadeh and Mansouri Daneshvar, 2020).	137
In the Fariman area, northeast Iran, numerous travertine springs align with fault	138
and fracture trends, often corresponding to inner faults. Over time, travertine	139
springs have led to the leaching of toxic elements from alteration zones into local	140
water sources. Given the extensive distribution of travertine springs in Chahar	141
Takab village, their alignment with faults, and the significant human population	142
relying on these waters for drinking, agriculture, and other purposes, we aim to	143
assess the impact of travertine formations and the regional geology on major and	144
minor components in water and, therefore, their suitability for both human	145
consumption and sustaining aquatic ecosystems within the catchment area. This	146
objective aligns with the concerns highlighted in the United Nations World Water	147
Development Report 2022 regarding the lack of reliable data for area-specific	148
groundwater assessments to enable informed policies and groundwater	149
resources management.	150
2 Materials and methods	151
2.1 Study area	152
The study area lies between latitude 35°20' to 35°34' N and longitude 59°53' to	153
60°04' E. It includes Chahar Takab (35°29'56.8"N 59°53'15.6"E), a rural village	154
located in Fariman county, Razavi Khorasan province (northeast Iran), 25 km	155
south of Fariman city and 115 km southeast of Mashhad city (Figure 1). The study	156
area has a BSk climate according to the Köppen climate classification (World	157
Bank, 2021). Fariman city experiences cold and long winters. In the coldest	158
months (December and January) temperature can drop to -17°C while in the	159
hottest (July and August) can reach 36°C (Iran Data Portal, 2022). Annual rainfall	160
is in the range of 150 to 200 mm (Iran Data Portal, 2022).	161
The study area lacks Paleocene and Oligocene facies. The oldest geological unit	162
dates back to the Precambrian period and consists of a sequence of metamorphic	163
rocks (Iran Oil Company, 1957). Near Chahar Takab village, a Miocene rock	164
formation is present, characterized by layers of clay or siltstone interbedded with	165
conglomerate, along with limestone layers to the southeast (Iran Oil Company,	166
1957). A geological map with data of the United States Geological Survey is in	167
the supplementary material (Figure S1).	168

Figure 1. Location of the water sampling points.

2.2 In-situ parameters and water sampling

In-situ parameters were measured, and water samples were collected from 34 sampling points in July 2019. In situ parameters included pH, electrical conductivity (EC) and temperature. Two bottles of water (500 ml) were collected at each point. Each bottle was washed three times with local water prior to water collection and no air bubbles were allowed in the bottles after collection. Due to the limited water resources in travertine springs, samples were collected there with a syringe.

The points were categorized into three groups, as detailed in Table 1. Group 1 comprised samples from travertine springs located at high altitudes (average: 1776 m.a.s.l.). Group 2 consisted of surface water collected at the highest locations (1827 and 1957 m.a.s.l.). Group 3 involved various types of groundwater samples: springs, well water, and groundwater transported in aqueducts. Group 3 samples were collected at lower altitudes (average: 1578 m.a.s.l.), except for CRW1, CRW27, CRW30 and CRW32, which were collected at higher altitudes (1754 to 2097 m.a.s.l.).

2.3 Laboratory analysis

Samples were transported to the Central Laboratory of Ferdowsi University in Mashhad, Iran, where all laboratory analysis were conducted. To prevent any

reaction with oxygen, carbonate (CO_3^{2-}), bicarbonate (HCO_3^-) and total alkalinity (T) were measured immediately after sampling using the titration method with phenolphthalein and methyl orange, following ISO 9963-1:1996. Sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) was measured with a spectrophotometer (DU-6 Spectrophotometer, 420nm; BECKMAN) at 420 nm following Standard Methods 4500- SO_4^{2-} E with barium chloride (BaCl_2) and other reagents. Chloride (Cl^-) was determined by titration with silver nitrate (AgNO_3) and potassium chromate (K_2CrO_4 5%) following Standard Methods 4500- Cl^- B. Ca and Mg, were analyzed by titration with EDTA according to Standard Methods 3500-Ca B and Standard Methods 3500-Mg B. To analyze As and the rest of the metals, 100 ml of collected water samples were filtered (0.25 μm) and acidified to $\text{pH}<2$ with nitric acid to prevent metal oxidation (Ghosh et al., 2019). Potassium (K) and Sodium (Na) as well as As, Cd, Cr, Co, Pb, Mn, Ni, Zn were determined with an ICP-OES (76004555 SPECTRO ARCOS System).

Table 1. Coordinates and altitude of the sampling points

Group	Point	Latitude (North)	Longitude (East)	Altitude (masl)	Source of water
1 Travertine springs	CRW2	35° 29' 50.4"	59° 53' 53.7"	1761	Travertine spring (1)
	CRW3	35° 29' 48.6"	59° 53' 54.6"	1779	Travertine spring (2)
	CRW4	35° 29' 48.3"	59° 53' 55.0"	1783	Travertine spring (3)
	CRW5	35° 29' 48.2"	59° 53' 56.0"	1772	Travertine spring (4)
	CRW6	35° 29' 48"	59° 53' 55.9"	1794	Travertine spring (5)
	CRW7	35° 29' 47.9"	59° 53' 55.8"	1785	Travertine spring (6)
	CRW28	35° 29' 41"	59° 53' 57.0"	1761	Travertine spring (7)
2 Surface water	CRW8	35° 29' 8.8"	59° 54' 25.7"	1827	River water
	CRW9	35° 29' 10.7"	59° 54' 30.1"	1911	Waterfall
3 Ground water	CRW1	35° 29' 57.7"	59° 54' 7.7"	1754	Chahar Takab spring
	CRW10	35° 30' 6.2"	59° 53' 12.6"	1686	Drinking water
	CRW11	35° 33' 58.2"	59° 55' 22.5"	1502	Golesheikh village aqueduct
	CRW12	35° 33' 54.4"	59° 56' 9.9"	1488	Golesheikh village well
	CRW13	35° 33' 26.1"	59° 55' 2.1"	1502	Kalate Rostam aqueduct
	CRW14	35° 32' 46.5"	59° 57' 25.4"	1620	Mazare Bi Abe aqueduct
	CRW15	35° 32' 0"	59° 57' 25.4"	1460	Taraz Khaki village spring
	CRW16	35° 32' 2.7"	59° 59' 42.7"	1444	Taraz Khaki village aqueduct
	CRW17	35° 30' 58.6"	59° 58' 29.5"	1553	Golestan village aqueduct
	CRW18	35° 30' 36.3"	59° 59' 12.3"	1549	Kariz Balagh village aqueduct
	CRW19	35° 30' 45.2"	60° 0' 12.2"	1461	Kariz Balagh village spring
	CRW20	35° 30' 29.3"	60° 1' 20.9"	1460	Galayem aqueduct
	CRW21	35° 30' 49.1"	60° 1' 6.5"	1439	Heidar spring of Galayem village
	CRW22	35° 29' 14.2"	60° 1' 3.1"	1569	Chaharbid aqueduct
	CRW23	35° 29' 27.6"	60° 2' 40.4"	1461	Kariz Sokhte aqueduct (1)
	CRW24	35° 28' 42"	60° 3' 36.6"	1429	Chenarbo aqueduct
	CRW25	35° 29' 36"	60° 2' 8.7"	1451	Kariz Sokhte aqueduct (2)
CRW26	35° 31' 37.5"	60° 0' 5.2"	1448	Kariz Balagh aqueduct	
CRW27	35° 29' 32.9"	59° 54' 11.4"	1815	Spring surrounding the travertine springs	
CRW29	35° 29' 45"	59° 54' 2.0"	1737	Spring surrounding the travertine	
CRW30	35° 29' 33"	59° 56' 31.0"	2097	Aqueduct in front of Golesheikh village	
CRW31	35° 32' 7"	59° 53' 44.0"	1575	aqueduct in front of Mazare Bi Abe	
CRW32	35° 29' 28.3"	59° 57' 54.8"	1955	Spring surrounding Golestan village	
CRW33	35° 32' 17"	59° 57' 14.0"	1468	Spring before Mazare Bi Abe village	
CRW34	35° 31' 39"	59° 56' 10.0"	1530	Estakhr village aqueduct	

2.4 Hydrochemical facies and Piper diagrams	209
The concentrations of the major cations (Na ⁺ , K ⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺) and major anions (HCO ₃ ⁻ , CO ₃ ²⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , Cl ⁻) were used to determine the hydrochemical characteristics of water samples. These data were represented in a Piper diagram using D-Piper software (Moreno Merino et al., 2021). Piper diagrams classify water into 6 ranges or types: first type (calcium bicarbonate water, Ca-HCO ₃), second type (sodium chloride, Na-Cl), third type (calcium magnesium chloride, Ca-Mg-Cl), fourth type (calcium bicarbonate sodium, Ca-Na-HCO ₃), fifth type (calcium chloride, Ca-Cl) and sixth type (sodium bicarbonate, Na-HCO ₃).	210 211 212 213 214 215 216 217
The Piper diagram shows water type, ion exchange, element dissolution or deposition, as well as mixing with other waters (Hounslow, 2018; Shakoor et al., 2018).	218 219 220
2.5 Pearson correlation coefficient	221
Pearson correlation coefficients for major cations and anions, pH and EC in groundwater were calculated using SPSS software. Correlation analysis provides valuable insights into ions with common origins, as well as those contributing significantly to pH and EC levels in the water (Yousefi et al., 2018).	222 223 224 225
2.6 Metal Index (MI)	226
Metal Index (MI) introduced by Tamasi and Cini (2004) was calculated using trace elements data using the following formula.	227 228
$MI = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{Cf}{(MAC)_i}$	229
where Cf is the concentration of each element in water, MAC is the maximum allowable concentration for a metal element based on drinking water guidelines from various sources, including the World Health Organization (WHO, 2022): As (10 µg/l), B (2400 µg/l), Cd (3 µg/l), Cr (50 µg/l), Cu (2000 µg/l), Mn (80 µg/l), Ni (70 µg/l), Pb (10 µg/l), Se (40 µg/l); the European Union (European Parliament, 2020): Fe (200 µg/l); and the USEPA (USEPA, 2022): Zn (5000 µg/l). Finally, i represents the ith sample. A higher metal index value indicates a higher concentration of metals relative to the allowable limit and, therefore, lower water quality. If the concentration of a particular element is higher than the allowable limit (MI>1), the water is considered contaminated for that element. Conversely, if the concentration of an element is lower than the allowable limit (MI<1), the water is considered free of contamination by that element.	230 231 232 233 234 235 236 237 238 239 240 241

3 Results and discussion	242
3.1 In situ parameters	243
Temperature, pH and conductivity values are presented in Figure 2 and all the values are compiled in the supplementary material (Table S1). Results have been categorized into three groups based on water type, as shown in Table 1. Temperature in group 1 displayed the highest mean (average 22.4°C, range 17.5-28.5°C) compared to group 2 (average 15°C, range 14.5-15.5°C) and group 3 (average 18.5°C, range 14.5-25.5°C). pH exhibited a lower average within travertine springs of group 1 (average 6.94, range 6.17-7.66) compared to groups 2 (average 8.31, range 8.28-8.33) and 3 (average 7.93, range 7.26-8.92). Regarding conductivity, higher values were observed in the travertine springs of group 1 (average 8733 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, range 4780-12360 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) compared to surface water of group 2 (average 419 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, range 408-430 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) and groundwater of group 3 (average 1273 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, range 560-4850 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$). Sample 28 displayed some differences with other samples of group 1, including the lowest conductivity in this group, probably because was distant from the rest.	244 245 246 247 248 249 250 251 252 253 254 255 256 257
Results indicated that pH is lower and dissolved salts are higher in travertine springs, a characteristic attributed to their geothermal origins (Kano et al., 2019). These springs originate from groundwater that permeates limestone-rich geological formations, becoming enriched in Ca^{2+} and HCO_3^- through the dissolution of CaCO_3 by CO_2 present in the water (Hiatt et al., 2022; Luo et al., 2022). As water emerges from the springs, changes in pressure and temperature lead to CO_2 degassing, reducing the solubility of calcium carbonate and precipitating dissolved ions in the surrounding areas (Brilli and Giustini, 2023; Gao et al., 2023; Ranjbaran and Zamanzadeh, 2021; Wang et al., 2015). Travertine springs interestingly exemplify groundwater geochemistry influenced by the interaction between alkalinity and dissolved CO_2 (Brilli and Giustini, 2023; Ranjbaran and Zamanzadeh, 2021). The process of CO_2 uptake by water at depth and its release at the surface not only regulates pH and alkalinity but also drives the continuous formation and growth of travertine deposits around the spring.	258 259 260 261 262 263 264 265 266 267 268 269 270 271 272
None of the samples of group 1 meet the drinkability criteria set by the European Union (European Parliament, 2020). Specifically, all the samples within this group surpass the established conductivity limit of 2500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, and additionally, CRW2, CRW3, and CRW4 samples fall below the lower pH threshold within the prescribed range of 6.5-9.5. Conversely, the conductivities of samples in groups 2 and 3 remained below this limit.	273 274 275 276 277 278

279

Figure 2. Elevation, temperature, pH and electrical conductivity in three groups of water samples (group 1, travertine springs, red; group 2, surface water, green; group 3, groundwater, blue) collected in Chahar Takab, Fariman county, northeast Iran along with drinking water thresholds for pH (6.5) and conductivity (2500 µS/cm) set by the European Union (European Parliament, 2020).

280

281

282

283

284

3.2 Concentrations of the major cations (Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺) and major anions (HCO₃⁻, CO₃²⁻, SO₄²⁻, Cl⁻)

285

286

As detailed in the supplementary material (Table S1), the predominant anion in group 1 samples was Cl⁻ (average 1462 mg/l, range 504-2190 mg/l), followed by HCO₃⁻ (average 1002 mg/l, range 622–1391 mg/l) while in groups 2 and 3, HCO₃⁻ was the predominant anion (averages 198 and 309 mg/l, ranges 195–201 and 238–421 mg/l, respectively). Among cations, Na showed the highest concentrations (average 1200 mg/l, range 435–1808 mg/l) in group 1. Group 2 presented similar levels of Ca (average 70 mg/l) and Mg (average 100 mg/l), while in group 3, Mg exhibited the highest concentration (average 254 mg/l, range 90–790 mg/l).

287

288

289

290

291

292

293

294

295

The European Union and the USEPA set a limit of 250 mg/l Cl⁻ and 200 mg/l Na in drinking water (European Parliament, 2020; USEPA, 2023, 2022). All group 1 samples and some in group 3 exceeded these limits and therefore, are unsuitable for drinking, while all groups 2 samples remained within the permissible range.

296

297

298

299

Defining thresholds for Ca and Mg in drinking water remains a challenge. Several researchers have proposed that minimum levels of approximately 20 to 30 mg/l

300

301

Ca and 10 mg/l Mg in drinking water could yield health benefits, including reduced cardiovascular mortality (WHO, 2005). The World Health Organization also indicate that the taste threshold for Ca ions falls within the range of 100–300 mg/l, depending on the associated anion, and suggests that the taste threshold for Mg is probably lower than that for Ca (WHO, 2022). In the case of Ca, all the samples in group 1 and some in group 3 are above these limits indicating suboptimal characteristics for drinking water. In the case of Mg, samples in group 1 well exceed the threshold, as well as most of the samples of groups 2 and 3.

Elevated Na in groundwater and springs is often attributed to the weathering of plagioclases, which have a high Na content, such as albite in igneous rocks. Also, to other Na-containing silicate minerals, such as nepheline, part of the feldspathoid group and present in igneous rocks. Furthermore, the presence of minerals such as halite and mirabilite in evaporitic rocks has also been associated with increased Na concentrations (Nugraheni and Sunjaya, 2019). In the study area, high Na concentrations exhibit a strong correlation with Cl ($R^2=0.8$) in group 1 samples, with a slope of 1.1. This slope is close to the 1:1 ratio typically associated with halite weathering, suggesting that halite dissolution is likely the primary source of these elevated ion concentrations (Zhang et al., 2020).

Sulfates concentrations were higher in group 1 (average 33.1 mg/l, range 14.4-55.3 mg/l) and lower in group 3 (average 13.3 mg/l, range 0.02-48.5 mg/l) and group 2 (average 0.12 mg/l, range 0.08-0.16 mg/l). All measured samples fell below the World Health Organization limit of 250 mg/l for sulfates in drinking water. Similar to Ca and Mg, this limit serves as a guideline for public acceptability and taste detection rather than as a health-based guideline (WHO, 2022). The predominant source of SO_4^{2-} has been associated with reactions of water and travertine rock (Hamidian et al., 2019). These results show an increase on sulfate concentrations in group 1 samples, where travertine is present, while the baseline sulfate concentration in group 3 samples remain relatively low. This difference is likely attributed to the reduced presence of sulfate-bearing minerals in the geological formations of group 3 areas. Concerning bicarbonates, travertine spring waters of group 1 exhibited elevated levels of HCO_3^- (average 1002 mg/l, range 622–1391 mg/l) due to limestones decomposition (Kano et al., 2019) compared to group 2 (average 198 mg/l, range 195–201 mg/l) and group 3 (average 309 mg/l, range 238–421 mg/l). This concentration in group 1 was likely different when the water was still underground. When groundwater rises to the surface, CO_2 dissolved in water evaporates because of the new equilibrium with the very low CO_2 content of the air, therefore, the pH increases, bicarbonate decreases and carbonate increases (Ulloa-Cedamanos et al., 2020). If calcium

ions were present in water, both would precipitate as CaCO_3 (Ulloa-Cedamano et al., 2020).

Based on the geological units displayed in the map in Figure S1, i.e. Q: Quaternary; Pg: Paleogene; Pz: Paleozoic; K: Cretaceous, unit K shows higher concentrations of all ions, lower pH, and higher EC. These values are attributed to the presence of travertine springs within this unit. In contrast, no significant differences are observed between units Pg and Pz, except for Na and Cl, which are higher in Pg compared to Pz.

3.3 Hydrochemical facies and Piper diagrams

The piper diagram (Piper, 1944) is depicted in Figure 3. In the present study, group 1 samples belong to third type (calcium magnesium chloride, Ca-Mg-Cl). Group 2 samples are classified as the first type (calcium bicarbonate water, Ca- HCO_3). Within group 3, most samples align with the first type, although one sample aligns with the third type (calcium magnesium chloride, Ca-Mg-Cl), and another with the fourth type (calcium bicarbonate sodium, Ca-Na- HCO_3).

The lithology and mineralogy of the aquifer determines the hydrochemical facies type found in the groundwater. The predominance of calcium bicarbonate (Ca- HCO_3) in group 2 and 3 indicates the dissolution of calcite and carbonate rocks. In the travertine springs of group 1, the abundance of Ca and Mg ions indicates a large ion exchange process.

Figure 3. Piper diagram of water samples collected in three groups of waters (group 1, travertine springs; group 2, surface water; group 3, groundwater) located in Chahar

3.4 Pearson correlation coefficient

364

Pearson correlation coefficients are presented in Table 2. The significant relationships among pH, EC and HCO_3^- can be attributed to the close contact between travertine spring water and CaCO_3 . Consequently, these waters exhibit higher level of EC and HCO_3^- , and also a lower pH due to the contact with CO_2 (Luo et al., 2022). EC displays a positive and very strong correlation with all the main anions and cations, except CO_3^{2-} , which is explained by the dependence of EC on dissolved ions.

A strong positive correlation is observed between HCO_3^- and Na, particularly in group 1. This aligns with the findings of Guettaf et al. (2017), who noted that elevated HCO_3^- in water increases the deposition of CaCO_3 and MgCO_3 , and therefore proportionally increases concentrations of Na. Moreover, As and sulfate have a positive and significant correlation, suggesting their concurrent release into the water. Thus, As and B can be linked to the oxidation of sulfide minerals in regenerative mineralization, in addition to travertine sources.

Table 2. Pearson correlation coefficients between hydrochemical parameters in waters from Chahar Takab, Fariman county, northeast Iran.

379

380

	pH	EC	CO_3^{2-}	HCO_3^-	Cl^-	SO_4^{2-}	Ca^{2+}	Mg^{2+}	Na^+	K^+
pH	1									
EC	-0.61**	1								
CO_3^{2-}	0.38	0.25	1							
HCO_3^-	-0.81**	0.88**	-0.02	1						
Cl^-	-0.59**	0.98**	0.26	0.84**	1					
SO_4^{2-}	-0.23	0.63**	0.37*	0.50**	0.62**	1				
Ca^{2+}	-0.70**	0.67**	0.42	0.84**	0.65**	0.38*	1			
Mg^{2+}	-0.62**	0.96**	0.10	0.85**	0.95**	0.58**	0.58**	1		
Na^+	-0.57**	0.96**	0.24	0.83**	0.95**	0.61**	0.69**	0.90**	1	
K^+	-0.50**	0.95**	0.37*	0.78**	0.94**	0.66**	0.61**	0.87**	0.94**	1

* Significance at the significance level of 0.05

381

** Significance at the significance level of 0.01

382

3.5 Heavy metals analysis and Metal Index (MI)

383

The results of the heavy metal analysis are depicted in Figure 4 and detailed in the supplementary material (Table S2). Group 1 samples showed the highest metal concentration averages in the cases of As, B, Cd, Cu, Fe, Mn, Zn and Se.

The average concentrations of several elements in groups 1, 2 and 3 surpassed the drinking water standards established by the World Health Organization

387

388

(WHO, 2022). Specifically, the average concentrations of As in groups 1 and 2 389
 (285 µg/l; 15.4 µg/l), B in group 1 (21660 µg/l), Fe in groups 1 and 3 (680 µg/l; 390
 176 µg/l), Mn in group 1 (215 µg/l) and Pb in group 1 (12.1 µg/l). Furthermore, 391
 several individual samples exhibited metal concentrations that exceeded the 392
 mentioned standards, as indicated in Figure 4. On the contrary, the average 393
 values of Cd, Cr, Cu, Mn, Ni, Zn, and Se, were lower. 394

Notably, As concentrations in group 1 samples were exceptionally high, 395
 exceeding the 10 parts per billion (ppb) limit set by World Health Organization 396
 (WHO, 2022), the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA, 397
 2022) and the European Union (European Parliament, 2020). These results 398
 suggest that most of the heavy metals in the waters are related to travertine 399
 springs in the region. However, the occurrence of As in natural waters is related 400
 to the water-rock interaction process (Kalender et al., 2015). 401

Figure 4. Concentrations of trace elements in three groups of waters (group 1: 403
 travertine springs, red; group 2: surface water, green; group 3: groundwater, blue) 404
 located in Chahar Takab, Fariman county, northeast Iran, and comparison with the 405
 World Health Organization’s drinking water limits (WHO, 2022) indicated by black 406
 horizontal lines. If a horizontal line is not present, the limit exceeds the range of the 407
 graph or is not defined. 408

Figure 5 illustrates the Metal Index (MI). Results show that 58% of all sampling 409
 points have values exceeding one. Group 1 exhibits the highest average MI value 410
 (44.99), surpassing the averages of group 2 (2.38) and group 3 (2.74). Within 411
 group 1, CRW3 and CRW4 stands out with exceptionally high MI values of 86.13 412
 and 61.95, respectively. In Group 3, CRW29 is notable for its elevated MI value 413

of 12.41. The contribution of individual metals to the MI calculation in group 1 414
 reveals values exceeding one for As (28.53), B (9.03), Fe (3.40), and Pb (1.21). 415
 A summary of non-potable samples and their parameters failing to meet the 416
 drinking water standards set by the World Health Organization (2022) and the 417
 European Union (2020) is provided in Table 3. 418

Figure 5. Metal index values in sampling points across three water groups (group 1: 420
 travertine springs, red; group 2: surface water, green; group 3: groundwater, blue) 421
 located in Chahar Takab, Fariman county, northeast Iran. 422

Table 3. Non potable samples and parameters exceeding the drinking water limits 423
 recommended by the World Health Organization (2022) and the European Union (2020). 424

	Sample ID	Parameter										
Group 1	CRW2	pH	conductivity	Cl-	Na ⁺	As	B	Fe	Mn			
	CRW3	pH	conductivity	Cl-	Na ⁺	As	B	Fe	Mn			
	CRW4	pH	conductivity	Cl-	Na ⁺	As		Fe	Mn			
	CRW5	conductivity	Cl-	Na ⁺	As	B						
	CRW6	conductivity	Cl-	Na ⁺	As	B						
	CRW7	conductivity	Cl-	Na ⁺	As	B						
	CRW28	conductivity	Cl-	Na ⁺	As		Cd	Cu		Pb		
Group 2	CRW8					As						
	CRW9					As						
Group 3	CRW13					As						
	CRW15	conductivity	Cl-	Na ⁺				Fe				
	CRW16			Na ⁺								
	CRW22							Fe				
	CRW24							Fe				
	CRW26							Fe				
	CRW27					As		Fe				
	CRW29					As	B	Fe	Mn			
CRW33	conductivity	Cl-	Na ⁺									
Permissible limits	WHO (2022)			250	200	10	2400	3	2000	200	80	10

	European Parliament (2020)	6.5-9.5	2500
--	----------------------------	---------	------

425

Figure 6 illustrates the proportions of trace-elements-associated risk classes within the 3 groups of water samples according to the guidelines proposed by the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe for the maintenance of aquatic life (UNECE, 1994), as described in Table 4. In summary, samples of group 1 have the highest toxicity risk, with three metals (As, Cd, Pb) having samples classified in class 2 or higher. In contrast, group 3 displays toxic risks for only two elements (Pb and Cd), and group 2 only for one element (Pb). Therefore, Pb shows toxicity in all groups, reaching class 4 in group 1. Cd exhibits toxic associated risks in group 1 and 3, reaching class 4 in group 1. Finally, As shows toxicity risk of class 2 in most of the samples of group 1. Cr, Cu, Ni and Zn fall completely in class 1 in all the groups and therefore, toxicity is not expected.

426
427
428
429
430
431
432
433
434
435
436

Table 4. United Nations Economic Commission for Europe freshwater quality standard ($\mu\text{g/L}$) for the maintenance of aquatic life (UNECE, 1994).

437
438

Element	Class I	Class II	Class III	Class IV	Class V
As	<10	10-100	100-190	190-360	>360
Cd	<0.07	0.07-0.53	0.53-1.1	1.1-3.9	>3.9
Cr	<1	1.0-6	6.0-11	11.0-16	>16
Cu	<2	2.0-7	7.0-12	12.0-18	>18
Pb	<0.1	0.1-1.6	1.6-3.2	3.2-82	>82
Hg	<0.003	0.003-0.007	0.007-0.012	0.012-2.4	>2.4
Ni	<15	15-87	87-160	160-1400	>1400
Zn	<45	45-77	77-110	110-120	>120

Interpretation:
Class I: No anthropogenic pollution with inorganic matter;
Class II: Concentrations are below midpoint between natural and chronically toxic levels;
Class III: Concentrations are above midpoint between natural and chronically toxic levels;
Class IV: Excursions beyond chronic criteria occur, but do not establish chronically toxic conditions in terms of concentration levels, duration or frequency;
Class V: Excursions beyond chronic criteria concentrations allow acutely toxic conditions in terms of concentration levels, duration or frequency

439
440
441
442
443
444
445
446

447

Figure 6. Proportions of trace-elements-associated risk classes in 3 groups of water samples (group 1: travertine springs; group 2: surface water; group 3: groundwater) collected in Chahar Takab, Fariman county, northeast Iran following the guideline of UNECE United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (1994).

448

449

450

451

Beyond the immediate toxicity risks posed by heavy metal-contaminated drinking water, bioaccumulation can increase the risks to humans and other living beings. Some trace elements such As, Cd, Pb, and Hg can cause health problems even at low concentrations (Avigliano et al., 2019; Gupta et al., 2019).

452

453

454

455

4 Conclusion

456

This study highlights the importance of assessing the quality of groundwater, particularly in regions where it serves as a primary water source for human consumption and agricultural purposes. Chahar Takab village in Fariman county, northeast Iran, relies significantly on groundwater, with travertine springs playing a prominent role in the local water supply.

457

458

459

460

461

This research reveals the water quality variability of different water sources (travertine springs, surface water, and groundwater) within the study area and key role of travertine springs. When travertine springs were present, results showed lower pH, higher electrical conductivity, and higher concentrations of major ions and heavy metals. Considering World Health Organization guidelines for drinking water, the concentrations of As were especially relevant (exceeded by up to 28.5 times). Other elements such as B, Fe, Mn, and Pb, also exceeded acceptable levels to a lesser extent, while As, Cd, and Pb posed the highest toxicity risks for biota.

462

463

464

465

466

467

468

469

470

Considering these findings, it is recommended that local authorities and stakeholders take action to address water quality issues. This includes conducting regular monitoring of water quality parameters and implementing measures to mitigate heavy metal contamination where necessary. Furthermore, public awareness campaigns and the exploration of alternative water sources may be necessary to ensure the health and well-being of the local population. Further research into the sources and mechanisms of heavy metal contamination in the region is needed to develop effective remediation strategies and safeguard water resources for the future.

References

- Aju, C.D., Reghunath, R., Achu, A.L., Rajaneesh, A., 2022. Understanding the hydrogeochemical processes and physical parameters controlling the groundwater chemistry of a tropical river basin, South India. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 29, 23561–23577. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-17455-w>
- Amaral, S.L., Azevedo, L.B., Buzalaf, M.A.R., Fabricio, M.F., Fernandes, M.S., Valentine, R.A., Maguire, A., Zohoori, F. V., 2018. Effect of chronic exercise on fluoride metabolism in fluorosis-susceptible mice exposed to high fluoride. *Sci. Rep.* 8, 3211. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-21616-2>
- American Cancer Society, 2020. Arsenic and Cancer Risk [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.cancer.org/healthy/cancer-causes/chemicals/arsenic.html> (accessed 7.3.22).
- Avigliano, E., Monferrán, M. V., Sánchez, S., Wunderlin, D.A., Gastaminza, J., Volpedo, A. V., 2019. Distribution and bioaccumulation of 12 trace elements in water, sediment and tissues of the main fishery from different environments of the La Plata basin (South America): Risk assessment for human consumption. *Chemosphere* 236, 124394. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.Chemosphere.2019.124394>
- Ayotte, J.D., Belaval, M., Olson, S.A., Burow, K.R., Flanagan, S.M., Hinkle, S.R., Lindsey, B.D., 2015. Factors affecting temporal variability of arsenic in groundwater used for drinking water supply in the United States. *Sci. Total Environ.* 505, 1370–1379. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.02.057>
- Bhowmick, S., Pramanik, S., Singh, P., Mondal, P., Chatterjee, D., Nriagu, J., 2018. Arsenic in groundwater of West Bengal, India: A review of human health risks and assessment of possible intervention options. *Sci. Total Environ.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.08.216>
- Biswas, R., Sarkar, A., 2019. Characterization of arsenite-oxidizing bacteria to decipher their role in arsenic bioremediation. *Prep. Biochem. Biotechnol.* 49(1), 30–37. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10826068.2018.1476883>
- Biswas, R., Vivekanand, V., Saha, A., Ghosh, A., Sarkar, A., 2019. Arsenite oxidation by a facultative chemolithotrophic *Delftia* spp. BAs29 for its potential application in groundwater arsenic bioremediation. *Int. Biodeterior. Biodegrad.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibiod.2018.10.006>
- Brilli, M., Giustini, F., 2023. Geochemical stratigraphy of the Prima Porta travertine deposit (Roma, Italy). *Minerals* 13, 789. <https://doi.org/10.3390/min13060789>
- Chakraborti, D., Rahman, M.M., Ahamed, S., Dutta, R.N., Pati, S., Mukherjee,

S.C., 2016. Arsenic groundwater contamination and its health effects in Patna district (capital of Bihar) in the middle Ganga plain, India. <i>Chemosphere</i> 152, 520–529. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2016.02.119	517 518 519 520
Delkhahi, B., Nassery, H.R., Vilarrasa, V., Alijani, F., Ayora, C., 2020. Impacts of natural CO ₂ leakage on groundwater chemistry of aquifers from the Hamadan Province, Iran. <i>Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control</i> 96, 103001. https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ijggc.2020.103001	521 522 523 524
Durowoju, O., Odiyo, J., Ekosse, G.I., 2015. Hydrogeochemical setting of geothermal springs in Limpopo Province, South Africa. <i>Res. J. Chem. Environ.</i> 19, 77–88.	525 526 527
European Parliament, 2020. Directive (EU) 2020/2184 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2020 on the quality of water intended for human consumption [WWW Document]. URL https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2020/2184/oj (accessed 6.8.22).	528 529 530 531
Foster, S.A., Pennino, M.J., Compton, J.E., Leibowitz, S.G., Kile, M.L., 2019. Arsenic Drinking Water Violations Decreased across the United States following Revision of the Maximum Contaminant Level. <i>Environ. Sci. Technol.</i> 53, 11478–11485. https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b02358	532 533 534 535
Gao, W., Zhang, J., Sun, D., Zhang, W., Wang, S., Guo, J., Xu, H., Zhao, S., Zeng, Y., Liu, X., 2023. Water Environmental Characteristics and Eutrophication Evaluation of Alpine Karst Mountains in Huanglong, Sichuan, China. <i>ACS Earth Sp. Chem.</i> 7, 1083–1096. https://doi.org/10.1021/acsearthspacechem.3c00015	536 537 538 539 540
Ghosh, S., Majumder, S., Roychowdhury, T., 2019. Assessment of the effect of urban pollution on surface water-groundwater system of Adi Ganga, a historical outlet of river Ganga. <i>Chemosphere</i> 237, 124507. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2019.124507	541 542 543 544
Grootjans, A., Bulte, M., Wołejko, L., Pakalne, M., Dullo, B., Eck, N., Fritz, C., 2015. Prospects of damaged calcareous spring systems in temperate Europe: Can we restore travertine-marl deposition? <i>Folia Geobot.</i> 50, 1–11. https://doi.org/10.1007/s12224-015-9214-z	545 546 547 548
Guettaf, M., Maoui, A., Ihdene, Z., 2017. Assessment of water quality: a case study of the Seybouse River (North East of Algeria). <i>Appl. Water Sci.</i> 7, 295–307. https://doi.org/10.1007/s13201-014-0245-z	549 550 551
Gupta, N., Yadav, K.K., Kumar, V., Kumar, S., Chadd, R.P., Kumar, A., 2019. Trace elements in soil-vegetables interface: Translocation, bioaccumulation, toxicity and amelioration - A review. <i>Sci. Total Environ.</i> 651, 2927–2942. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.10.047	552 553 554 555
Hamidian, A.H., Razeghi, N., Zhang, Y., Yang, M., 2019. Spatial distribution of arsenic in groundwater of Iran, a review. <i>J. Geochemical Explor.</i> 88–98. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gexplo.2019.03.014	556 557 558
He, S., Wu, J., 2019a. Hydrogeochemical Characteristics, Groundwater Quality, and Health Risks from Hexavalent Chromium and Nitrate in Groundwater of Huanhe Formation in Wuqi County, Northwest China. <i>Expo. Heal.</i> 11, 125–137. https://doi.org/10.1007/s12403-018-0289-7	559 560 561 562
He, S., Wu, J., 2019b. Relationships of groundwater quality and associated health risks with land use/land cover patterns: A case study in a loess area, Northwest China. <i>Hum. Ecol. Risk Assess. An Int. J.</i> 25, 354–373. https://doi.org/10.1080/10807039.2019.1570463	563 564 565 566

He, X., Li, P., Ji, Y., Wang, Y., Su, Z., Elumalai, V., 2020. Groundwater Arsenic and Fluoride and Associated Arsenicosis and Fluorosis in China: Occurrence, Distribution and Management. <i>Expo. Heal.</i> 12, 355–368. https://doi.org/10.1007/s12403-020-00347-8	567 568 569 570
Henchiri, M., Ben Ahmed, W., Brogi, A., Alçiçek, M.C., Benassi, R., 2017. Evolution of pleistocene travertine depositional system from terraced slope to fissure-ridge in a mixed travertine-alluvial succession (Jebel El Mida, Gafsa, Southern Tunisia). <i>Geodin. Acta</i> 29, 20–41. https://doi.org/10.1080/09853111.2016.1265398	571 572 573 574 575
Hiatt, C.D., Newell, D.L., Jessup, M.J., Grambling, T.A., Scott, B.E., Upin, H.E., 2022. Deep CO ₂ and N ₂ emissions from Peruvian hot springs: Stable isotopic constraints on volatile cycling in a flat-slab subduction zone. <i>Chem. Geol.</i> 595, 120787.	576 577 578 579
Hossain, S., Hosono, T., Ide, K., Matsunaga, M., Shimada, J., 2016. Redox processes and occurrence of arsenic in a volcanic aquifer system of Kumamoto Area, Japan. <i>Environ. Earth Sci.</i> 75, 740. https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-016-5557-x	580 581 582 583
Hounslow, A.W., 2018. <i>Water quality data: Analysis and interpretation</i> , First. ed, Water Quality Data: Analysis and Interpretation. CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, USA. https://doi.org/10.1201/9780203734117	584 585 586
Huq, M.E., Fahad, S., Shao, Z., Sarven, M.S., Khan, I.A., Alam, M., Saeed, M., Ullah, H., Adnan, M., Saud, S., Cheng, Q., Ali, S., Wahid, F., Zamin, M., Raza, M.A., Saeed, B., Riaz, M., Khan, W.U., 2020. Arsenic in a groundwater environment in Bangladesh: Occurrence and mobilization. <i>J. Environ. Manage.</i> 262, 110318. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.110318	587 588 589 590 591
IPCC, 2022. Sixth Assessment Report Fact sheet - Food and Water.	592
Iran Data Portal, 2022. Iran Meteorological Organization [WWW Document]. URL https://irandataportal.syr.edu/iran-meteorological-organization (accessed 3.18.22).	593 594 595
Iran Oil Company, 1957. Geological Map of Iran [WWW Document]. URL https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/geological-map-iran (accessed 8.28.23).	596 597 598
Islam, M.S., 2023. Introduction to Hydrogeochemical Processes, in: Islam, M.S. (Ed.), <i>Hydrogeochemical Evaluation and Groundwater Quality</i> . Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-44304-6_1	599 600 601
Janssens, N., Capezzuoli, E., Claes, H., Mucchez, P., Yu, T.L., Shen, C.C., Ellam, R.M., Swennen, R., 2020. Fossil travertine system and its palaeofluid provenance, migration and evolution through time: Example from the geothermal area of Acquasanta Terme (Central Italy). <i>Sediment. Geol.</i> 398, 105580. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sedgeo.2019.105580	602 603 604 605 606
Kalender, L., Öztekin Okan, Ö., Inceöz, M., Çetindağ, B., Yildirim, V., 2015. Geochemistry of travertine deposits in the eastern anatolia district: An example of the karakoçan-yoğunağaç (elazığ) and mazgirt-dedebağ (tunceli) travertines, Turkey. <i>Turkish J. Earth Sci.</i> 24, 607–626. https://doi.org/10.3906/yer-1504-27	607 608 609 610 611
Kampouroglou, E.E., Economou-Eliopoulos, M., 2016. Assessment of the environmental impact by As and heavy metals in lacustrine travertine limestone and soil in Attica, Greece: Mapping of potentially contaminated sites. <i>Catena</i> 139, 137–166. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2015.12.009	612 613 614 615
Kano, A., Okumura, T., Takashima, C., Shiraishi, F., 2019. Geomicrobiological	616

- Properties and Processes of Travertine, Springer Geology. Springer 617
Singapore, Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-1337-0> 618
- Kele, S., Bódai, B., 2022. Age, Depositional Environment, and Geochemistry of 619
Freshwater Carbonates (Travertine, Tufa) from Hungary, in: Veress, M., 620
Leél-Óssy, S. (Eds.), Cave and Karst Systems of Hungary. Cave and Karst 621
Systems of the World. Springer. 622
- Kumar, R., Patel, M., Singh, P., Bundschuh, J., Pittman, C.U., Trakal, L., Mohan, 623
D., 2019. Emerging technologies for arsenic removal from drinking water in 624
rural and peri-urban areas: Methods, experience from, and options for Latin 625
America. *Sci. Total Environ.* 694, 133427. 626
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.07.233> 627
- Luo, L., Capezzuoli, E., Rogerson, M., Vaselli, O., Wen, H., Lu, Z., 2022. 628
Precipitation of carbonate minerals in travertine-depositing hot springs: 629
Driving forces, microenvironments, and mechanisms. *Sediment. Geol.* 438, 630
106207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sedgeo.2022.106207> 631
- Masoudinejad, M., Ghaderpoori, M., Zarei, A., Nasehifar, J., Malekzadeh, A., 632
Nasiri, J., Ghaderpoury, A., 2018. Data on phosphorous concentration of 633
rivers feeding into Taham dam in Zanjan, Iran. *Data Br.* 17, 564–569. 634
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2018.01.068> 635
- Mohammadzadeh, H., Mansouri Daneshvar, M.R., 2020. A comparison of hydro- 636
geochemistry and stable isotope composition of travertine-depositing 637
springs, Garab in NE Iran and Pamukkale in SW Turkey. *Carbonates and 638
Evaporites* 35, 23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13146-020-00566-9> 639
- Moreno Merino, L., Aguilera, H., González-Jiménez, M., Díaz-Losada, E., 2021. 640
D-Piper, a modified piper diagram to represent big sets of hydrochemical 641
analyses. *Environ. Model. Softw.* 138, 104979. 642
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2021.104979> 643
- Mueller, B., 2017. Arsenic in groundwater in the southern lowlands of Nepal and 644
its mitigation options: A review. *Environ. Rev.* 25, 296–305. 645
<https://doi.org/10.1139/er-2016-0068> 646
- Nugraheni, R.D., Sunjaya, D., 2019. Geochemical Approach to Reveal the 647
Genetic Occurrence of Gibbsite, Relative to the Parent Rock Type in Lateritic 648
Bauxites. *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* 1363, 012042. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1363/1/012042> 649
650
- Ortega-Guerrero, A., 2017. Evaporative concentration of arsenic in groundwater: 651
health and environmental implications, La Laguna Region, Mexico. *Environ. 652
Geochem. Health* 39, 987–1003. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10653-016-9866-5> 653
654
- Pazhoor, M.T., Gautam, P.K., Samanta, S., Suman, Bangotra, P., Banerjee, S., 655
2021. Performance assessment of Zn–Sn bimetal oxides for the removal of 656
inorganic arsenic in groundwater. *Groundw. Sustain. Dev.* 14, 100600. 657
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gsd.2021.100600> 658
- Piper, A.M., 1944. A graphic procedure in the geochemical interpretation of water- 659
analyses. *Eos, Trans. Am. Geophys. Union* 25, 914–928. 660
<https://doi.org/10.1029/TR025I006P00914> 661
- Pola, M., Gandin, A., Tuccimei, P., Soligo, M., Deiana, R., Fabbri, P., Zampieri, 662
D., 2014. A multidisciplinary approach to understanding carbonate 663
deposition under tectonically controlled hydrothermal circulation: A case 664
study from a recent travertine mound in the Euganean hydrothermal system, 665
northern Italy. *Sedimentology* 61, 172–199. 666

https://doi.org/10.1111/sed.12069	667
Pollastro, R., Persits, F., Steinshouer, D.W., 1999. Surficial geology of Iran (geo2cg) [WWW Document]. U.S. Geol. Surv. data release. URL https://doi.org/10.5066/P93ZEPFY (accessed 1.10.25).	668 669 670
Ranjbaran, M., Zamanzadeh, S.M., 2021. Determining the role of chemical and biological factors in controlling precipitation of tufa and travertine deposits in Shurab area, Northern Iran. <i>Carbonates and Evaporites</i> 36, 73.	671 672 673 674
https://doi.org/10.1007/s13146-021-00691-z	674
Rezaei, A., Hassani, H., Hayati, M., Jabbari, N., Barzegar, R., 2018. Risk assessment and ranking of heavy metals concentration in Iran's Rayen groundwater basin using linear assignment method. <i>Stoch. Environ. Res. Risk Assess.</i> 32, 1317–1336. https://doi.org/10.1007/s00477-017-1477-x	675 676 677 678
Roh, T., Lynch, C.F., Weyer, P., Wang, K., Kelly, K.M., Ludewig, G., 2017. Low-level arsenic exposure from drinking water is associated with prostate cancer in Iowa. <i>Environ. Res.</i> 159, 338–343. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2017.08.026	679 680 681 682
Shakeri, A., Sharifi Fard, M., Mehrabi, B., Rastegari Mehr, M., 2020. Occurrence, origin and health risk of arsenic and potentially toxic elements (PTEs) in sediments and fish tissues from the geothermal area of the Khiav River, Ardebil Province (NW Iran). <i>J. Geochemical Explor.</i> 106347. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gexplo.2019.106347	683 684 685 686 687
Shakoor, M.B., Bibi, I., Niazi, N.K., Shahid, M., Nawaz, M.F., Farooqi, A., Naidu, R., Rahman, M.M., Murtaza, G., Lüttge, A., 2018. The evaluation of arsenic contamination potential, speciation and hydrogeochemical behaviour in aquifers of Punjab, Pakistan. <i>Chemosphere</i> 199, 737–746. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.02.002	688 689 690 691 692
Shiraishi, F., Morikawa, A., Kuroshima, K., Amekawa, S., Yu, T.L., Shen, C.C., Kakizaki, Y., Kano, A., Asada, J., Bahniuk, A.M., 2020. Genesis and diagenesis of travertine, Futamata hot spring, Japan. <i>Sediment. Geol.</i> 405, 105706. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sedgeo.2020.105706	693 694 695 696
Tamasi, G., Cini, R., 2004. Heavy metals in drinking waters from Mount Amiata (Tuscany, Italy). Possible risks from arsenic for public health in the Province of Siena. <i>Sci. Total Environ.</i> 327, 41–51. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2003.10.011	697 698 699 700
Tapia, J., Murray, J., Ormachea, M., Tirado, N., Nordstrom, D.K., 2019. Origin, distribution, and geochemistry of arsenic in the Altiplano-Puna plateau of Argentina, Bolivia, Chile, and Perú. <i>Sci. Total Environ.</i> 678, 309–325. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.04.084	701 702 703 704
Ulloa-Cedamanos, F., Probst, J.L., Binet, S., Camboulive, T., Payre-Suc, V., Pautot, C., Bakalowicz, M., Beranger, S., Probst, A., 2020. A Forty-Year Karstic Critical Zone Survey (Baget Catchment, Pyrenees-France): Lithologic and Hydroclimatic Controls on Seasonal and Inter-Annual Variations of Stream Water Chemical Composition, pCO ₂ , and Carbonate Equilibrium. <i>Water</i> 2020, Vol. 12, Page 1227 12, 1227. https://doi.org/10.3390/W12051227	705 706 707 708 709 710 711
UNECE United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, 1993. Standard Statistical Classification of Surface Freshwater Quality for the Maintenance of Aquatic Life, in: <i>Readings in International Environment Statistics</i> . United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, United Nations, New York and Geneva, p. 546.	712 713 714 715 716

UNESCO World Water Assessment Programme, 2022. The United Nations World Water Development Report 2022: groundwater: making the invisible visible.	717 718 719
United Nations, 2022. The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2022.	720
USEPA, 2023. National Recommended Water Quality Criteria - Aquatic Life Criteria Table [WWW Document]. URL https://www.epa.gov/wqc/national-recommended-water-quality-criteria-aquatic-life-criteria-table (accessed 7.17.23).	721 722 723 724
USEPA, 2022. Table of Secondary Standards. Secondary Drinking Water Standards: Guidance for Nuisance Chemicals [WWW Document]. URL https://www.epa.gov/sdwa/secondary-drinking-water-standards-guidance- nuisance-chemicals (accessed 5.10.22).	725 726 727 728
USEPA, 2004. Evaluation of the potential carcinogenicity of arsenic compounds [WWW Document]. URL https://cfpub.epa.gov/si/si_public_record_Report.cfm?Lab=ORD&dirEntryID=41925 (accessed 7.3.22).	729 730 731 732
Vardhan, K.H., Kumar, P.S., Panda, R.C., 2019. A review on heavy metal pollution, toxicity and remedial measures: Current trends and future perspectives. <i>J. Mol. Liq.</i> https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2019.111197	733 734 735
Wang, X., Zhou, X., Zhao, J., Zheng, Y., Song, C., Long, M., Chen, T., 2015. Hydrochemical evolution and reaction simulation of travertine deposition of the Lianchangping hot springs in Yunnan, China. <i>Quat. Int.</i> 374, 62–75. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2014.09.046	736 737 738 739
WHO, 2022. Guidelines for drinking-water quality, 4th edition, incorporating the 1st and 2nd addenda. Geneva.	740 741
WHO, 2005. Nutrients in Drinking Water.	742
World Bank, 2021. Climate change knowledge portal [WWW Document]. URL https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/iran-islamic-rep (accessed 8.31.22).	743 744 745
World Meteorological Organization, 2022. Protect our people and future generations: Water and Climate Leaders call for urgent action [WWW Document]. URL https://public.wmo.int/en/media/press-release/protect-our-people-and-future-generations-water-and-climate-leaders-call-urgent (accessed 3.18.23).	746 747 748 749 750
Yousefi, M., Dehghani, M.H., Nasab, S.M., Taghavimanesh, V., Nazmara, S., Mohammadi, A.A., 2018. Data on trend changes of drinking groundwater resources quality: A case study in Abhar. <i>Data Br.</i> 17, 424–430. https://doi.org/10.1016/J.DIB.2018.01.032	751 752 753 754
Zhang, Y., Zhou, X., Liu, H., Hai, K., Yu, M., Tan, M., 2020. Characterization of a saline hot spring depositing travertine in the red beds in the Simao Basin of China. <i>Hydrogeol. J.</i> 28, 1431–1447. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10040-020-02126-w	755 756 757 758 759 760

Statements & Declarations

- Competing interests

The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

- CRedit authorship contribution statement

M.R.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing

M.H.M-G.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision

N.F.: Resources, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision

D.R.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization, Supervision.

Supplementary material

Figure S1. Surficial geology of the study area. Geologic Units: Q: Quaternary; Pg: Paleogene; Pz: Paleozoic; K: Cretaceous. Source: Pollastro et al. (1999) for U.S. Geological Survey.

Table S1. Hydrochemical parameters considered in this study.

	Sample ID	Elevation	T(°C)	pH	EC	CO ₃ ²⁻	HCO ₃ ⁻	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	Na ⁺	K ⁺
Group 1	CRW2	1761	23.5	6.17	7890	0	1196	1338	22.7	860	830	1231	129
	CRW3	1779	21.0	6.25	9300	0	1391	1547	36.7	450	950	1075	132
	CRW4	1783	17.5	6.31	7630	0	1165	1216	24.4	740	800	1034	127
	CRW5	1772	28.5	7.37	8650	0	921	1529	31.0	350	920	1555	169
	CRW6	1794	22.5	7.66	10520	36	933	1911	47.3	540	870	1262	211
	CRW7	1785	21.0	7.52	12360	21	787	2190	55.3	100	1260	1808	290
	CRW28	1761	23.0	7.33	4780	0	622	504	14.4	80	730	435	8.6
	Average	1776	22.4	6.94	8733	8.1	1002	1462	33.1	446	909	1200	152
	Max	1794	28.5	7.66	12360	36	1391	2190	55.3	860	1260	1808	290
	Min	1761	17.5	6.17	4780	0	622	504	14.4	80	730	435	8.6
Group 2	CRW8	1827	15.5	8.33	408	9	195	17.4	0.08	70	100	24.5	3.7
	CRW9	1955	14.5	8.28	430	12	201	17.4	0.16	70	100	18.07	2.8
	Average	1891	15.0	8.31	419	10.5	198	17.4	0.12	70	100	21.3	3.3
	Max	1955	15.5	8.33	430	12	201	17.4	0.16	70	100	24.5	3.7
	Min	1827	14.5	8.28	408	9	195	17.4	0.08	70	100	18.1	2.8
Group 3	CRW1	1754	18.2	7.70	635	0	268	34.8	0.06	90	180	30.8	3.4
	CRW10	1686	20.5	7.46	713	0	360	34.8	0.02	20	250	38.2	5.5
	CRW11	1502	16.3	7.26	1337	6	397	104	8.77	40	320	35.3	12.7
	CRW12	1488	15.1	7.46	877	0	262	69.5	14.2	70	190	77.1	8.7
	CRW13	1502	14.5	7.54	1420	0	421	156	5.6	120	290	93.3	14.3
	CRW14	1620	19.5	7.75	560	6	262	34.8	35.6	70	160	33.6	4.5
	CRW15	1460	25.5	7.72	3560	12	384	660	12.1	80	500	425	39.7
	CRW16	1444	16.5	8.28	1207	15	244	86.9	15.5	230	90	632	11.2
	CRW17	1553	16.4	8.07	1553	6	256	34.8	6.87	50	220	35.5	6.3
	CRW18	1549	16.5	7.73	687	3	238	17.4	7.02	70	190	32.1	6.8
	CRW19	1461	15.5	7.82	702	0	275	34.8	7.30	60	170	38.4	10.7
	CRW20	1460	17.3	7.90	730	15	262	34.8	14.2	70	130	52.1	7.5
	CRW21	1439	22.5	8.46	1423	0	342	122	6.71	50	280	115	14.2
	CRW22	1569	24.5	8.21	671	15	311	34.8	11.8	110	120	31.1	8.4
	CRW23	1461	22.5	8.06	1175	3	281	69.5	12.2	120	180	77.8	11.4
	CRW24	1429	18.5	8.12	1215	6	275	104	10.4	130	160	85.8	10.6
	CRW25	1451	16.5	7.90	1038	6	305	52.1	8.43	120	190	62.3	11.2
	CRW26	1448	17.5	8.26	843	9	238	52.1	12.9	50	230	22.2	9.4
	CRW27	1815	17.5	7.94	1285	6	275	69.5	47.8	80	180	73.2	10.1
	CRW29	1737	16.2	7.61	1440	3	342	104	5.95	60	290	36.0	15.6
	CRW30	2097	20.1	7.94	595	9	305	34.8	12.0	20	250	7.0	4.7
	CRW31	1575	22.3	8.92	1204	12	299	69.5	10.4	60	260	67.2	12.9
	CRW32	1954	15.4	8.51	1038	6	299	69.5	48.5	110	370	21.1	5.2
CRW33	1468	23.5	7.70	4850	0	415	1147	10.7	60	790	480	30.7	
CRW34	1530	15.1	8.10	1065	3	421	52.1	8.77	50	360	26.1	7.9	
Average	1578	18.5	7.93	1273	5.6	309	131	13.3	79.6	254	105	11.3	
Max	2097	25.5	8.92	4850	15	421	1147	48.5	230	790	632	39.7	
Min	1429	14.5	7.26	560	0	238	17.4	0.02	20	90	7.0	3.4	
Totals	Average	1636	19.1	7.75	2759	6.4	446	399	16.6	154.4	380	326	39.9
	Max	2097	28.5	8.92	12360	36	1391	2190	55.3	860	1260	1808	290
	Min	1429	14.5	6.17	408	0	195	17.4	0.02	20	100	7.0	2.8
	EU			6.5-9.5	2500			250				200	
	WHO			6.5-8.5					250	300	100		
	USEPA							250				200	

Table S2. Heavy metal concentrations in water samples ($\mu\text{g/l}$), metal index (MI) and permissible limits considered in this study from World Health Organization, European Union and USEPA.

783
784
785

	Sample ID	As	B	Cd	Cr	Cu	Fe	Mn	Ni	Pb	Se	Zn	MI
Group 1	CRW2	87.7	22435	0.25	2.79	7.62	1538	299	3.81	1.01	1.52	19.8	29.49
	CRW3	658	24324	0.27	1.95	12.5	1290	274	3.62	0.83	1.39	14.8	86.13
	CRW4	482	2068	0.22	2.21	9.97	1794	284	3.54	1.55	1.55	16.4	61.95
	CRW5	312	26088	0.00	2.17	109	25.9	4.54	2.96	0.00	1.38	3.55	42.38
	CRW6	164	33125	2.39	2.15	13.4	27.1	13.4	3.83	0.23	1.43	5.51	31.45
	CRW7	137	43560	0.40	2.42	17.6	47.1	8.08	7.07	1.01	0.00	6.87	32.55
	CRW28	157	23.0	7.33	6.58	3193	40.8	622	14.4	80	1.13	730	36.24
	Average	285	21660	1.55	2.90	480	680	215	5.60	12.1	1.20	114	44.99
	Max	658	43560	7.33	6.58	3193	1794	622	14.4	80	1.55	730	86.13
Min	87.7	23	0.00	1.95	7.62	25.9	4.54	2.96	0.00	0.00	3.55	29.89	
Group 2	CRW8	15.9	377	0.20	4.53	2.88	40.8	6.18	3.71	1.85	0.82	0.82	2.44
	CRW9	14.8	287	0.19	4.09	2.34	40.6	4.68	5.85	1.56	1.56	0.78	2.29
	Average	15.4	332	0.20	4.31	2.61	40.7	5.43	4.78	1.71	1.19	0.80	2.37
	Max	15.9	377	0.20	4.53	2.88	40.8	6.18	5.85	1.85	1.56	0.82	2.44
	Min	14.8	287	0.19	4.09	2.34	40.6	4.68	3.71	1.56	0.82	0.78	2.29
Group 3	CRW1	0.5	255	0.00	6.88	0.89	32.1	3.44	0.06	2.42	1.60	0.00	0.78
	CRW10	3.3	306	0.00	5.23	2.90	42.4	5.61	4.64	4.64	2.13	1.35	1.43
	CRW11	9.5	1281	0.34	15.2	1.90	47.0	5.02	8.31	0.86	1.73	2.59	2.45
	CRW12	7.1	901	0.18	17.6	1.50	70.3	5.62	8.25	4.12	1.87	1.68	2.5
	CRW13	12.2	1543	0.22	15.1	1.55	48.7	4.66	6.88	2.44	0.44	0.22	2.9
	CRW14	0.8	238	0.18	7.52	0.94	47.8	4.89	6.20	2.82	1.88	0.18	1.1
	CRW15	3.9	1765	0.20	8.76	5.09	347	6.72	7.74	1.22	3.87	2.03	3.52
	CRW16	2.9	470	0.00	24.6	1.66	56.8	7.30	7.30	1.04	1.25	0.20	1.6
	CRW17	2.4	253	0.00	9.17	0.72	44.2	4.58	6.27	0.48	0.48	0.72	0.96
	CRW18	7.9	207	0.19	8.06	0.39	49.2	4.32	5.70	1.77	0.59	20.5	1.67
	CRW19	1.0	262	0.20	0.20	1.24	35.9	7.88	6.27	4.35	0.83	0.00	1.11
	CRW20	0.8	366	0.25	9.68	0.25	52.0	4.58	5.09	0.25	0.76	1.52	0.94
	CRW21	3.0	677	0.00	9.02	1.93	42.3	10.5	8.37	0.85	1.93	0.42	1.36
	CRW22	1.0	261	0.19	7.55	1.19	850	8.54	6.16	4.37	0.00	0.59	5.3
	CRW23	2.9	618	0.00	10.9	0.13	57.9	4.89	6.01	0.00	2.00	0.00	1.25
	CRW24	0.0	622	0.20	10.9	1.41	465	7.88	6.27	2.42	0.8	0.60	3.32
	CRW25	2.1	533	0.00	10.0	1.04	42.2	10.2	5.85	3.97	1.25	0.41	1.48
	CRW26	0.1	334	0.14	10.0	1.19	728	8.08	6.13	1.04	0.74	0.89	4.35
	CRW27	20.6	1175	0.00	7.00	1.31	477	7.87	6.12	2.84	0.43	0.65	5.55
	CRW29	37.7	8756	0.22	6.58	4.77	482	176	7.26	0.68	0.31	5.67	12.41
	CRW30	0.0	2005	0.15	6.94	2.68	75.7	5.36	6.62	3.31	1.20	8.99	1.93
	CRW31	3.1	184	0.20	6.41	2.20	52.7	17.4	6.41	4.00	0.76	0.60	1.57
	CRW32	1.0	1253	0.19	13.8	3.64	127	6.91	9.21	2.88	0.74	0.00	2.12
	CRW33	1.8	206	0.24	6.23	0.99	63.4	6.48	5.74	0.99	2.85	0.74	1.12
CRW34	0.1	1946	0.25	11.2	7.51	56.3	13.7	7.51	1.29	0.89	4.40	1.85	
Average	5.0	1057	0.14	9.79	1.96	176	13.9	6.41	2.20	1.25	2.20	2.58	
Max	37.7	8756	0.34	24.6	7.51	850	176	9.21	4.64	3.87	20.5	12.41	
Min	0.0	184	0.00	0.20	0.13	32.1	3.44	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.78	
Totals	Average	63.3	5256	0.61	7.45	178	296	68.1	6.16	6.01	1.21	42.6	11.42
	Max	658	43560	7.33	24.6	3193	1794	622	14.4	80	3.87	730	111.78
	Min	0	23	0.00	0.2	0.13	25.9	3.44	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.20
	Permissible limits (WHO, 2022)	10	2400	3	50	2000	200	80	70	10	40	5000	

786
787
788